

Effect of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on Teachers' Productivity in North-West Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the effect of information and communication technology on teachers' productivity in North-West region. The aim was to determine how each identified ICT facility affected teachers' productivity (research improvement, teaching, and student evaluation). The study adopted a survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 596 academic staff from seven schools within the four selected Federal Colleges of Education in the region. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to determine the sample size and instrument administration. A questionnaire was used for data collection. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient, yielded reliability indices of 0.81, 0.80, and 0.79 for the respective sections, indicating that the instrument was reliable since the calculated indices were closer to 1. A multiple linear regression model was used for data analysis. Findings showed that the various ICT predictors have varying levels of significance on teachers' productivity (research, teaching, and student evaluation). The significant predictors aver that integrating ICT into research, teaching, and student evaluation, makes the teacher more productive. While the non-significant predictors possibly establish gaps in the integration and usage of the ICT tools by instructors. The recommendation is that education stakeholders should develop and enforce institutional policies that promote digital literacy and encourage teachers to use ICT for research, teaching, and student evaluation. =

Keywords: ICT, Teachers, Productivity, Research, Teaching, Evaluation

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been found to be important to improving teachers' productivity. This is because research, lesson preparation, material delivery, evaluation, and professional development are all made easier by ICTs. This gives teachers the required tools needed to research and teach more effectively and efficiently. By increasing teacher productivity and instructional quality, ICT adoption has the potential to address some of the educational challenges that persist in North-West Nigeria, including low student performance, persistent insecurity, teacher shortages, and inadequate instructional resources (Yusuf & Balogun, 2011). Because of this, countries are now investing more in ICT tools to help teachers be more productive.

Effective management of classroom activities, research visibility, provision of high-quality education, and evaluation of student learning results are frequently used to gauge a teacher's productivity. According to Umoren (2019), incorporating interactive and multimedia ICT capabilities into the teaching increased teachers' engagement and interaction with students, which in turn increased their productivity. It has been demonstrated that using ICT tools, such as interactive whiteboards, educational software, and online learning platforms, has no doubt increased teachers' motivation. The impact of ICT use on instructor productivity has significant ramifications for Nigerian educational institutions.

However, despite the global push for ICT integration in education, Adeosun, (2010) stresses that many teachers in North-West Nigeria continue to encounter obstacles such as limited access to digital devices, a lack of technical skills, and inadequate infrastructure. Concerns regarding the degree to which ICT usage affects teacher productivity in the area are raised by these difficulties. In light of this, the study uses a multiple regression analysis to investigate the effect of ICT on teachers' productivity in North-West, Nigeria. According to Voogt and Knezek (2018), information and communication technology (ICT) usage is the efficient use of digital tools, communication networks, and computing technologies to improve a range of

tasks, such as administration, teaching, and learning. ICT utilization in the classroom refers to the application of tools like computers, projectors, interactive whiteboards, and online resources to enhance teacher effectiveness, assessment, and the delivery of instruction. The level of ICT utilization by instructors more commonly depends on various aspects such as access to digital technologies, digital literacy abilities, institutional support, and pedagogical attitudes.

To increase productivity and efficiency, Kumar et al., (2019), argued that teachers have to integrate ICTs for administrative tasks like lesson planning, managing student records, and communicating with stakeholders. Furthermore, Law, Pelgrum, and Plomp, (2008) opined that ICTs promote ongoing professional development by facilitating teacher cooperation through digital resource sharing, professional learning networks, and online forums. Umoren (2019) provided evidence to support this assertion, arguing that the use of innovative teaching techniques, like interactive whiteboards, educational software, and online resources, improved the way examples were presented and fostered student cooperation. He reiterated that in order for instructors to fully understand the potential advantages of ICT, they must be well-prepared and have a greater interest in the ICT framework. However, a supportive environment comprising institutional policies, training, and infrastructure is necessary for efficient ICT use. Nigeria and many other developing nations continue to struggle with issues like poor ICT infrastructure, spotty internet access, and a dearth of teacher ICT training programs (Ololube, 2015). Overcoming these constraints is vital for ensuring that instructors can leverage the benefits of ICTs to boost productivity and educational results.

According to Hanushek and Rivkin (2010), teacher productivity is the capacity of educators to successfully provide high-quality instruction, oversee classroom activities, support student learning outcomes in a learning environment and contribute to knowledge through research. It is frequently gauged by how well a teacher implements the curriculum, which includes class planning, lesson planning, student participation, and standard assessment procedures. Similarly, Yusuf and Balogun, (2011) looked into the relationship between teacher motivation and productivity in Nigeria. They insisted that motivated teachers had higher levels of commitment to their work and production. Motivational factors like cash rewards, acknowledgement, and a positive work atmosphere were essential for raising teacher productivity. As a result, good instructors frequently exhibit great teaching abilities, flexibility, and the capacity to make use of existing ICTs to improve instruction.

In this regard, Goe, Bell, and Little (2008) stress that teachers who have access to ongoing ICT training and professional development opportunities typically conduct research, deliver lessons and improve student performance more successfully. However, the benefits of ICTs on teacher productivity have been limited, especially in developing regions like North-West Nigeria, as a result of issues including digital illiteracy, a lack of infrastructure, and teacher reluctance to change and adopt new research and teaching methods in schools. Information and communication technology (ICT) use in education has been the subject of numerous empirical researches, which have highlighted the effects of ICTs on research, student learning, teaching effectiveness, and general school administration. Utilization of ICTs improves instructional delivery and raises teacher involvement, which increases the effectiveness of education. A study by Awudu and Attah (2024) found that the presence of ICT facilities like computers, software, online databases, and digital libraries significantly supports research productivity among academic staff. They also discovered that integrating ICT into student evaluation by academic staff enhances the impartiality of assessments.

In a similar vein, Yusuf and Balogun (2011) found that student-teachers in Nigeria who received ICT training were more proficient in lesson delivery and evaluation techniques than those who did not. These results imply that, when used properly, ICTs can act as a catalyst to enhance the teaching-learning process. The study conducted by Law, Pelgrum, and Plomp (2008), revealed that ICT-supported teaching methods improved teacher motivation and professional development, which in turn raised productivity. They did point out, though, that teacher attitudes, technological access, and institutional regulations all affected the degree of ICT adoption. Notwithstanding the advantages of ICTs in education, several studies have shown obstacles that prevent its efficient application. In underdeveloped nations like Nigeria, Ololube (2015) emphasized issues like poor infrastructure, spotty internet access, and inadequate teacher preparation. Similarly, a study by Kumar, Rose, and D'Silva (2019) discovered that poor support from school administration, resistance to change by teachers, and a lack of technical skills were the main reasons why instructors were reluctant to adopt ICTs. To improve ICT adoption in education, these studies highlight the necessity of funding ICT infrastructure and ongoing professional development. The above literature highlights the value of ICTs in contemporary education and the necessity of their broad implementation in Nigeria's educational milieu.

It is glaring that there has been significant advancement in the availability and usage of ICT facilities in Nigerian educational institutions. Institutions of learning have different degrees of availability and usage of ICT facilities such as computers, projectors, digital libraries, learning management systems, internet access, among many others. The impact of these tools on teachers' productivity largely depends on the level of integration into teaching practices. Thus, it is against this backdrop that this research becomes imperative in evaluating the extent to which ICT tools positively affect teachers' productivity, in the Federal Colleges of Education.

Objectives of the study

1. To find out how ICT facilities improve research among teachers in Federal Colleges of Education, Northwest Nigeria.
2. To investigate how the ICT facilities affect teaching in the study area.
3. To identify the effects of ICT tools on students' evaluation in the study area.

Research questions

1. What are the effects of ICT facilities on research output among teachers in Federal Colleges of Education, Northwest geopolitical Zone?
2. What are the effects of ICT facilities on teaching in the study area?
3. What are the effects of ICT tools on students' evaluation in the study area?

Methodology

This study adopts a survey design to identify the effect of information and communication technology on teachers' productivity in North-West, Nigeria. The study was centered on four Federal Colleges of Education in the region. The selected colleges were FCE Zaria, FCE Kano, FCE Technical Bichi, and FCE Technical Gusau, known for significant academic manpower. This was before FCE Zaria, and FCE Kano were converted to the Federal University of Education. The study's population consisted of 596 academic staff from seven schools within the four selected Federal Colleges of Education. The study used a multi-stage sampling technique. The selected Colleges of Education were done purposively in the first stage. The second stage involved organizing schools within these colleges into seven strata. The third stage involved randomly selecting a department from each stratum. Finally, questionnaires were randomly distributed to the sampled respondents. The study adopted the Research Advisors (2008) table, which recommended a sample size of 217 for a total population of 596, with a 95% confidence level, 50% variability, and a ± 5 margin of error. Expecting a minimum return of 95% (173 responses), 9 questionnaires were included to account for the margin of error, resulting in a sample size of 182. However, proportional sampling across departments brought the total sample size to approximately 184. A total of 184 questionnaires were administered to teachers across seven selected departments from four colleges of education. A total of 163 questionnaires were returned, representing an 89% response rate. The questionnaire has three sections, covering ICT utilization in research, the effectiveness of ICT in teaching, and the importance of ICT in students' evaluation. The reliability of the questionnaire was pre-tested using the Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient, yielding reliability indices of 0.81, 0.80, and 0.79 for the respective sections, indicating that the instrument was reliable, as supported by Obeka (2011). The collected data were analyzed using inferential statistics: multiple linear regression. The model is specified thus:

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8 + \beta_9 X_9 + \beta_{10} X_{10} + \beta_{11} X_{11} + \beta_{12} X_{12} + \mu$$

Where:

Y = Dependent Variable and X = Independent Variable

Y = Teachers' productivity (research, teaching and learning, and students evaluation).

α_0 = Intercept

$B_1 - B_{12}$ = Coefficient of all the Independent Variable;

$X_1 - X_{12}$ = Independent Variables. Thus:

X_1 = Desktop/laptop computers

X_2 = Reliable internet access

X_3 = Secure Wi-fi network/wired connections available in offices, libraries/computer labs

X_4 = Institutional e-mail accounts

X_5 = Video conferencing software for virtual meetings and communications

X_6 = Access to online databases, and journals

X_7 = Statistical analysis software and tools

X_8 = E-Library resources/services

X_9 = Projectors/interactive whiteboards

X_{10} = Learning Management System (LMS)

X_{11} = Training and workshops on the usage of ICT tools

X_{12} = Professional development in emerging technologies and pedagogical approaches

A Priori expectations:

$\beta_1 > 0, \beta_2 > 0, \beta_3 > 0, \beta_4 > 0, \beta_5 > \beta_6 > 0, \beta_7 > 0, \beta_8 > 0, \beta_9 > 0, \beta_{10} > 0, \beta_{11} > 0, \beta_{12} > 0$

Where:

α_0 is the intercept or the constant term,

β_1 to β_{12} represent the slope coefficients,

μ is the stochastic term or the error term.

Results

Research question 1: How do ICT facilities affect research output among teachers in Federal Colleges of Education, Northwest geopolitical Zone?

Regression Coefficients of ICT and improvement on teachers' research

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	5.399	.410		13.154	.000
	Desktop/laptop computers	-.016	.080	-.016	-.201	.041
	Reliable internet access	-.260	.112	-.210	-2.317	.022
	Secure Wi-fi network or wired connections available in offices, libraries, and computer labs	.019	.114	.015	.165	.869
	Institutional e-mail accounts	-.016	.077	-.018	-.208	.835
	Video conferencing software for virtual meetings and communications	.002	.094	.002	.025	.980
	Access to online databases, and journals	.042	.085	.042	.492	.024
	Statistical analysis software and tools	-.334	.089	-.320	-3.751	.000
	E-Library resources/services	-.193	.090	-.195	-2.131	.035
	Projectors/interactive whiteboards	.137	.088	.121	1.548	.124
	Learning Management System (LMS)	-.103	.098	-.075	-1.060	.291
	Training and workshops on the usage of ICT tools	-.080	.089	-.068	-.905	.367
	Professional development in emerging technologies and pedagogical approaches.	-.118	.078	-.112	-1.509	.133

1. Dependent Variable: improvement on teachers' research

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

To analyze the effect of information and communication technology on the improvement of teachers' research from the data collected, a multiple linear regression was used. The analysis showed a good model fit: $F(12,150) = 5.612, p < .001$; $AdjR^2 = .255$ and $R^2 = .310$. The analysis shows that ICT facilities like Desktop/laptop computers, internet access, online databases and journals, statistical analysis software and tools, and e-library resources/services had positive effects on teachers'

research at $B=.16$, $t=-.201$, $p=.041$; $B=-.260$, $t=-2.317$, $p=.022$; $B=.042$, $t=.492$, $p=.024$; $B=-.334$, $t=-3.751$, $p=.001$; and $B=-.193$, $t=-2.131$, $p=.035$ respectively.

However, secure Wi-fi network or wired connections available in offices, libraries, and computer labs ($B=.019$, $t=.165$, $p=.869$), Institutional e-mail accounts ($B=-.016$, $t=-.208$, $p=.835$), video conferencing software for virtual meetings and communications ($B=.002$, $t=.025$, $p=.980$), projectors/interactive whiteboards ($B=.137$, $t=1.548$, $p=.124$), Learning Management System ($B=-.103$, $t=-1.060$, $p=.291$), training and workshops on the usage of ICT tools ($B=-.080$, $t=-.905$, $p=.367$), and professional development in emerging technologies and pedagogical approaches ($B=-.118$, $t=-1.509$, $p=.133$) had negative effect on teachers' improvement in research.

Research question 2: What are the effects of ICT facilities on teaching in the study area?

Regression Coefficients of ICT and Teaching

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.402	.537		8.195	.000
	Desktop/laptop computers	-.356	.149	-.250	-2.397	.018
	Reliable internet access	-.037	.147	-.025	-.249	.804
	Secure Wi-fi network or wired connections available in offices, libraries, and computer labs	.086	.104	.073	.821	.413
	Institutional e-mail accounts	.110	.100	.104	1.092	.276
	Video conferencing software for virtual meetings and communications	.086	.123	.072	.699	.486
	Access to online databases, and journals	-.022	.111	-.019	-.199	.843
	Statistical analysis software and tools	-.041	.117	-.033	-.351	.726
	E-Library resources/services	-.229	.118	-.196	-1.930	.046
	Projectors/interactive whiteboards	-.018	.116	-.014	-.155	.877
	Learning Management System (LMS)	-.201	.128	-.124	-1.572	.118
	Training and workshops on the usage of ICT tools	.216	.116	.156	1.857	.045
	Professional development in emerging technologies and pedagogical approaches.	-.078	.102	-.063	-.761	.048

2. Dependent Variable: Teaching

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Table 2 shows the multiple linear regression of the effect of information and communication technology on teaching among the selected teachers in the sample area. The analysis showed a good model fit: $F(12,150) = 2.134$, $p < .018$; $AdjR^2 = .078$ and $R^2 = .146$. The results reveal that ICT tools such as Desktop/laptop computers ($B=-.356$, $t=-2.397$, $p=.018$), e-library resources/services ($B=-.229$, $t=-1.930$, $p=.046$), training and workshops on the usage of ICT tools ($B=.216$, $t=1.857$, $p=.045$), and Professional development in emerging technologies and pedagogical approaches ($B=-.078$, $t=-.761$, $p=.048$) all had positive effects on teaching and learning.

Also, the results found a negative effect of internet access ($B=-.037, t=-.249, p=.804$), secure Wi-fi network or wired connections available in offices, libraries, and computer labs ($B=.086, t=.821, p=.413$), institutional e-mail accounts ($B=.110, t=1.092, p=.276$), video conferencing software for virtual meetings and communications ($B=.086, t=.699, p=.486$), access to online databases, and journals ($B=-.022, t=-.199, p=.843$), statistical analysis software and tools ($B=-.041, t=-.351, p=.726$), projectors/interactive whiteboards ($B=-.018, t=-.155, p=.877$), and Learning Management System ($B=-.201, t=-1.572, p=.118$) on teaching and learning.

Research question 3: What are the effects of ICT tools on students' evaluation in the study area?

Regression Coefficients of ICT and students' evaluation

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	42.131	3.006		14.018	.000
	Desktop/laptop computers	-.366	.159	-.250	-2.389	.017
	Reliable internet access	-.361	.818	-.040	-.441	.660
	Secure Wi-fi network or wired connections available in offices, libraries, and computer labs	.825	.815	.093	1.012	.313
	Institutional e-mail accounts	-.540	.555	-.082	-.974	.332
	Video conferencing software for virtual meetings and communications	-.974	.630	-.131	-1.545	.124
	Access to online databases, and journals	.060	.588	.008	.103	.918
	Statistical analysis software and tools	-3.050	.636	-.419	-4.794	.000
	E-Library resources/services	.061	.553	.008	.109	.913
	Projectors/interactive whiteboards	.863	.637	.104	1.356	.177
	Learning Management System (LMS)	-.433	.749	-.042	-.578	.564
	Training and workshops on the usage of ICT tools	-.324	.088	-.322	-3.761	.000
	Professional development in emerging technologies and pedagogical approaches.	-1.830	.718	-.181	-2.548	.012

3. Dependent Variable: student evaluation

Source: Fieldwork (2024).

Analysis of data in Table 3 reveals the multiple linear regression of the effect of information and communication technology on student evaluation by teaching staff in the selected federal institutions of learning. The results showed a good model fit: $F(12,150) = 5.755, p < .001; AdjR^2 = .260$ and $R^2 = .315$. The analysis shows that utilization of desktop/laptop computers, statistical analysis software and tools, Training and workshops on the usage of ICT tools, and Professional development in emerging technologies and pedagogical approaches at $B=-.366, t=-2.389, p=.017; B=-3.050, t=-4.794, p=.000; B=-.324, t=-3.761, p=.000;$ and $B=-1.830, t=-2.548, p=.012;$ respectively had positive effect on students evaluation by teachers.

But, reliable internet access ($B=-.361, t=-.441, p=.660$), secure Wi-fi network or wired connections available in offices, libraries, and computer labs ($B=.825, t=1.012, p=.313$), institutional e-mail accounts ($B=-.540, t=-.974, p=.332$), video conferencing software for virtual meetings and communications ($B=-.974, t=-1.545, p=.124$), access to online databases and

journals ($B=.060$, $t=.103$, $p=.918$), e-library resources/services ($B=.061$, $t=.109$, $p=.913$), projectors/interactive whiteboards ($B=.863$, $t=1.356$, $p=.177$), and Learning Management System ($B=-.433$, $t=-.578$, $p=.564$), had negative effect on students evaluation by teachers.

Discussion of Findings

In analyzing the effect of ICT on teachers' productivity in the study areas, three variables were identified. These variables include research, teaching and learning, and student evaluation. A multiple regression was run to find out the effect of different ICT facilities on each of them. On teachers' productivity through research, the finding shows that desktop/laptop computers, internet access, online databases and journals, statistical analysis software and tools, and e-library resources/services are ICT resources that had statistically significant positive effects. This suggests that access to personal computing devices enhances research productivity. The finding also aligns with the expectation that reliable internet access facilitates research by providing access to information, communication, and collaboration tools. The ability to access scholarly materials is an essential component of academic research, and this result confirms its significance. Access to statistical tools also significantly contributes to research productivity, likely due to their necessity in data analysis. E-libraries on the other hand provide digital access to books, journals, and reference materials, which are fundamental in conducting literature reviews and referencing sources. This finding is supported by Awudu and Attah (2024) where through a descriptive study it was discovered that the presence of ICT facilities like computers, software, online databases, and digital libraries significantly supports research productivity among academic staff.

However, Wi-Fi networks/wired connections, institutional email accounts, video conferencing Software, projectors/Interactive whiteboards, Learning Management Systems (LMS), ICT training and workshops, and professional development in emerging technologies are predictors that did not show significant effects. This implies that they may not directly contribute to teachers' research productivity or that their influence is not strong enough. Four ICT-related tools were found to have a significant positive effect on teachers' productivity in teaching. These are desktop/laptop computers, e-library resources/services, training and workshops on ICT tools, professional development in emerging technologies and pedagogical approaches. Access to computer systems and digital academic resources positively influences teaching and learning, as they provide teachers and students with valuable reference materials and support independent learning. Training of teachers in ICT tools enhances their ability to integrate technology effectively into teaching, making lessons more engaging and improving pedagogical strategies. The statistically significant professional development implies that when educators engage in continuous learning about new technologies, they can improve their teaching methodologies. This validates the finding by Yusuf and Balogun (2011) that effective utilization of ICT tools is a catalyst that enhances the teaching-learning process. The finding also corroborated the study by Law, Pelgrum, and Plomp (2008). They argued that ICT-supported teaching methods improved teacher professional development, which in turn raised productivity. However, the negative coefficient in the predictors with significant p value indicates that an increase in the independent variable tends to decrease the dependent variable.

Again, the finding shows that ICT tools and resources internet access, secure wi-fi/wired connections, institutional email accounts, video conferencing software, statistical analysis software, projectors/interactive whiteboards, and LMS were not significantly associated with improved teaching outcomes in the study areas. This contrasts with the finding by Umoren (2019) who discovered that the use of innovative teaching techniques like interactive whiteboards, educational software, and online resources fostered student cooperation. This could be due to inconsistent access, quality issues, or limited effective use in pedagogical activities. This also shows that teachers might rely more on in-person interactions rather than virtual meetings for instructional delivery. The lack of evidence of a significant effect could also be possibly due to low usage by instructors as found by Awudu and Attah (2024) or limited interactive and innovative applicability in classroom settings.

From the analysis, the ICT tools found to significantly improve teachers' productivity in the evaluation of students are desktop/laptop computers, statistical analysis software and tools, training and workshops on ICT tools, and professional development in emerging technologies and pedagogical approaches. This suggests that access and utilization of these tools and training enhances teachers' ability to assess students effectively. Computers allow for efficient grading, assignment management, and data analysis for performance tracking and the ability to analyze student performance trends through statistical tools likely supports more objective and insightful evaluations. Moreso, better familiarity with digital assessment platforms and new educational technologies and pedagogical strategies equips the teacher and enhances grading efficiency and fairness. This corroborates the finding by Awudu and Attah, (2024) that ICT integration into student evaluation enhances the clarity and impartiality of assessments. The negative coefficient in the predictors with a significant p-value indicates that an increase in the independent variable tends to decrease the dependent variable.

However, we do not have evidence of the significant effect of predictors such as internet access, Wi-Fi, institutional emails, video conferencing software, projectors/Interactive whiteboards, LMS, and digital library resources on teachers' evaluations of students. This shows that while these tools are essential for instructional delivery, they may not directly influence students' assessment.

Conclusion

The study assesses the effect of ICT facilities on the productivity teachers in four Colleges of Education, in Nigeria's North-West Zone within the positivist research paradigm. ICT is a variable of interest in education. The findings reveal that utilization of ICT facilities such as internet access, Wi-fi network/wired connections, institutional e-mail accounts, video conferencing software for virtual meetings and communications, access to online databases, and journals, statistical analysis software and tools, e-library resources/services, projectors/interactive whiteboards, Learning Management System, training and workshops on the usage of ICT tools, and professional development in emerging technologies and pedagogical approaches by teachers in research, teaching, and evaluation of students has significant and non-significant effects. Leveraging ICT availability, and digital literacy for teachers through continuous training, and institutional policies that enforce their usage become necessary to enhance teachers' productivity.

Recommendations

To benefit more from ICT in research, teaching, and student evaluation, the following recommendations are made:

1. Federal Colleges of Education should prioritize investment in ICT resources that directly support research, teaching, and evaluation such as internet access, online databases, statistical tools, LSM, projectors/Interactive Whiteboards and e-libraries.
2. Since training workshops and professional development have had a significant impact, institutions should focus on practical software training on research-backed, interactive whiteboards, digital grading systems, data analysis, and assessment to enable teachers to integrate ICT tools effectively. This will further ensure that teachers receive practical guidance on how to use ICT tools specifically for academic research, teaching, and student evaluation
3. Education stakeholders should develop and enforce institutional policies that promote digital literacy and encourage teachers to use ICT for research and visibility, interactive whiteboards for effective teaching, and LMS-based grading systems and data analytics features to enhance evaluation quality.
4. Education stakeholders should regularly review and update the ICT strategy to ensure it remains relevant and responsive to teachers' evolving needs.

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